

TREAD: Token Routing for Efficient Architecture-agnostic Diffusion Training

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Abstract

Diffusion models have emerged as the mainstream approach for visual generation. However, these models typically suffer from sample inefficiency and high training costs. Consequently, methods for efficient finetuning, inference and personalization were quickly adopted by the community. However, training these models in the first place remains very costly. While several recent approaches including masking, distillation, and architectural modifications have been proposed to improve training efficiency, each of these methods comes with a tradeoff: they achieve enhanced performance at the expense of increased computational cost or vice versa. In contrast, this work aims to improve training efficiency as well as generative performance at the same time through routes that act as a transport mechanism for randomly selected tokens from early layers to deeper layers of the model. Our method is not limited to the common transformer-based model - it can also be applied to state-space models and achieves this without architectural modifications or additional parameters. Finally, we show that TREAD reduces computational cost and simultaneously boosts model performance on the standard ImageNet-256 benchmark in class-conditional synthesis. Both of these benefits multiply to a convergence speedup of $14\times$ at 400K training iterations compared to DiT and $37\times$ compared to the best benchmark performance of DiT at 7M training iterations. Furthermore, we achieve a competitive FID of 2.09 in a guided and 3.93 in an unguided setting, which improves upon the DiT, without architectural changes.

Project Page: <https://compvis.github.io/tread>

1. Introduction

In recent years, diffusion models [26, 54, 61] have become a powerful generative technique for image synthesis [54]. They have also been successfully extended to the 3D [51] and video domains [5]. While diffusion models avoid some training challenges faced by their predecessors, such as GANs [18], which are inherently unstable during training, they incur high costs [35] due to slow convergence and sample

Figure 1. We introduce TREAD, a training strategy that enables substantially more efficient training of token-based diffusion backbones. Applied to the standard backbone DiT [48], we achieve a $14/37\times$ training speed increase w.r.t. unguided FID while also converging to better generation quality.

inefficiency [44]. Currently, the Diffusion Transformer (DiT) [48] is the main backbone when training diffusion models, building on the established Transformer architecture [69]. However, the Transformer architecture has computational cost limitations, as it scales quadratically with token length and converges slowly, further increasing the cost of training diffusion models. Training a DiT on standard benchmarks alone requires thousands of A100 GPU hours without reaching convergence, and text-to-image models demand even more resources. Stable Diffusion [54], for instance, required about 150,000 A100 GPU hours. Despite ongoing efforts to reduce computational demands through improved infrastructure, implementation, and hardware, democratizing the training of diffusion models remains a distant goal. Methods such as LoRA [27] for parameter-efficient fine-tuning, caching strategies [43, 71] to accelerate inference, and approaches for personalization [4, 16, 28, 56] have made these aspects more accessible. However, full-scale training remains extremely costly, limiting broad participation in the development and improvement of diffusion models. Several works have proposed methods to accelerate training convergence utilizing external self-supervised features [29, 72],

Figure 2. Selected samples from ImageNet-256 generated with a DiT-XL/2+TREAD using a guidance weight of $\omega = 3.5$.

improved flow-based theory [20, 37, 59], or optimized data combinations [68, 74]. Another approach to reducing computational resource requirements is *masking*, where a subset of the available information is used during training. This subset can be selected either randomly [17, 75] or based on learned heuristics [45, 70], while the remaining information is permanently lost [7, 23]. Beyond masking, computational efficiency can also be improved by controlling the flow of information during training. Instead of discarding information, it can be selectively directed to specific computational blocks, allowing tokens to skip computations and reducing the overall workload. This process is known as *routing* [53].

These methods offer two potential advantages: **i)** reducing compute requirements by processing fewer tokens [21, 75], and **ii)** enhancing convergence by encouraging contextual relation learning [3, 17], thus addressing the lacking data efficiency and lowering computational demands. While masking has been extensively studied for both benefits and is a well-established technique in self-supervised [3] and representation learning [23], routing has primarily been considered from the viewpoint of compute reduction [24, 53].

This work explores the routing technique for diffusion models using a route that passes tokens from one layer to another layer deeper in the network. The loss of information is only temporary, as information will be reintroduced after the route concludes. We do this by defining a route with a start and end layer and a fixed ratio with which tokens are randomly selected for routing. This is done only during training and without any dynamic adaptations based on iterations or timesteps. Furthermore, we test a variety of configurations and derive clear guidelines for applying our routing mechanism to achieve substantial improvements in both qualitative performance and efficiency. Our main contributions can be summarized as follows:

- A novel training strategy for token-based sequential models that utilizes a token transport mechanism termed *routing*, which directs tokens from early into later network layer.
- An evaluation of the underlying routing mechanism, its effectiveness, and the derivation of empirically validated guidelines for its application.
- Significant improvements in both convergence per step and cost per step on the ImageNet-256 benchmark, leading to a substantial reduction in computational cost. This enables the training of state-of-the-art competitor models at a fraction of the cost without requiring architectural modifications.
- Finally, we reach an FID of **2.09** which improves upon the standard DiT training and results in a **37 \times** speedup.

2. Related Work

Diffusion Models and Efficient Generative Backbones. Score-based generative models [62, 63], like notably DDPMs [26], now lead image synthesis. They define a forward SDE that progressively adds Gaussian noise, mapping data to a standard Gaussian. An iterative denoising process is used to reverse this transformation and generate samples. A key improvement in the efficiency of early diffusion models was to train in a compressed latent space [54].

Building on the foundation of score-based models, early diffusion methods [8, 26, 54] used the UNet backbone [55], while more recent token-based architectures like DiT [48] and its variants [6, 10, 75] have gained preference, despite their quadratic complexity in the number of tokens.

To address computational challenges associated with token-based models, recent work introduces caching for UNet-based diffusion [41] or DiT-based models [42]. Unlike these approaches, our method instead applies a training-time

routing mechanism that moves tokens between layers, improving efficiency without omitting necessary computations.

Alongside diffusion transformers, state-space models (SSMs) have emerged as promising alternatives to DiTs [12, 14, 30, 67] to mitigate quadratic complexity. Explorations of token pruning [73], token masking [65] and mixture-of-experts [50] for SSMs have not targeted diffusion backbones, whereas we consider token routing in SSMs as well to boost overall training efficiency and convergence.

Token-based Routing, Pruning and Masking. Several recent methods [13, 47, 64] utilize Mixture-of-Experts (MoE) [31, 60] to improve the efficiency of diffusion transformers. Typically, MoE is implemented as a router module that divides parts of the network, such as single FFNs, into parallel parts, called “experts”. The router then determines which expert processes each token, thereby reducing computational overhead compared to applying every parameter to every token. Another strategy, Mixture-of-Depths (MoD) [53], involves a router module that decides the computation paths for each token within the network, allowing tokens to skip certain computational blocks. MoD has been shown to decrease runtime costs while maintaining model performance in transformer-based language models. In contrast to these methods, our approach does not require a routing module. Instead, we introduce a training strategy that enhances efficiency without modifying the base architecture.

To further address the scalability issues associated with attention, numerous studies [11, 45, 52, 70] have focused on pruning tokens based on their content, such as similarity or redundancy. This token pruning helps reduce the computational burden of the attention mechanism by eliminating less important tokens. While our approach selects tokens, they are skipping the computations in certain layers, it differs from prior works in that our routing scheme makes these tokens available again in deeper parts of the network and does not rely on the content of the tokens. Instead of pruning based on token content, our method employs a routing mechanism that directs tokens through the network irrespective of their content, maintaining computational efficiency.

In addition to pruning-based methods, recent advancements like MaskDiT [17, 75] have proposed token masking schemes applicable to DiTs. MaskDiT improves efficiency by significantly lowering the cost per iteration and accelerating training while matching the performance of standard DiTs. Based on this, SD-DiT [76] enhances generative quality by incorporating a discriminative loss alongside the masking strategy. Similar to these approaches, our scheme directs tokens to later layers at random. However, unlike MaskDiT, which replaces masked tokens with learnable embeddings, our method routes tokens back to later layers in the network.

Figure 3. **TREAD: Our method for efficient diffusion training.** In a) the standard training and inference strategy is shown where all tokens are processed by all layers of the network. TREAD enhances training efficiency by routing tokens around certain layers by reducing computational load and it preserves information which is shown in b). Since TREAD is used only during training, the standard setting shown in a) is used for inference.

3. TREAD

We adopt the continuous-time diffusion framework proposed by Karras et al. [32] (EDM), where the forward diffusion process transforms real data samples into progressively noisier versions through the addition of Gaussian noise:

$$\mathbf{x}_t = \mathbf{x}_0 + \mathbf{n}, \quad \mathbf{n} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, t^2 \mathbf{I}), \quad (1)$$

where t is the diffusion time.

The denoising network estimates the original data by minimizing the denoising diffusion objective:

$$\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{x}_0 \sim \mathcal{P}_{\text{data}}} \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{n} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, t^2 \mathbf{I})} \|D_\theta(\mathbf{x}_0 + \mathbf{n}, t) - \mathbf{x}_0\|^2. \quad (2)$$

To efficiently model global context, we represent inputs (x_t) through *tokens*, which are continuous vector embeddings of image patches or latent segments. Tokenization allows architectures such as DiT [48] or SSMs [30, 49] to capture long-range dependencies via global mixers.

Balancing Cost and Effectiveness. Training diffusion models is challenging due to their sample inefficiency and high computational demands. Two primary factors must be

balanced during optimization: *training cost* (iterations per second) and *training effectiveness* (performance gain per iteration). Increasing iterations per second reduces the cost per iteration, while improved training effectiveness lowers the overall compute time by achieving higher quality outputs in fewer steps. Many methods optimize one factor at the expense of the other, creating a trade-off between cost and effectiveness. For example, masking a subset of tokens [75] significantly enhances throughput in transformer networks, which are hindered by quadratic complexity $\mathcal{O}(n^2)$, and similar benefits are observed in SSMs [34]. Alternatively, training effectiveness is sometimes enhanced via architectural changes (e.g., additional parameters [66, 75]) or pretrained teacher models for representation distillation [72]. However, these architecture modifications generally compromise training efficiency as more parameters or additional models are required during training, whereas masking-based methods that enhance training effectiveness [7, 17, 23] are limited by the inherent drawback of permanent data loss.

Although masking can be used to trade training efficiency for effectiveness (or vice versa) [17, 75], it violates the core principle of diffusion, which relies on small, iterative denoising steps. Masking completely removes tokens from the information flow, requiring the model to reconstruct information solely from learnable substitutes [17, 23], thereby partially disrupting the process of incremental refinement. Despite this, the fact that the use of masking yields valid diffusion models demonstrates that it is still possible to learn the data distribution with a subset of tokens.

Routing: Information-Preserving Token Transport. To resolve the trade-off between training efficiency and training effectiveness, we introduce TREAD, a diffusion training strategy that preserves information and, therefore aligns with the core diffusion principle of incremental denoising steps. We achieve this through *routing*, where a subset of tokens is temporarily removed at a *start layer* and reintroduced at a later *end layer*, enabling token transport without permanently discarding information. This is presented in Figure 3. For standard token-based diffusion models, the denoiser is represented as a composition of layers:

$$D_\theta(\mathbf{x}) \equiv [L_{B-1} \circ L_{B-2} \circ \dots \circ L_0](\mathbf{x}), \quad (3)$$

where B denotes the total number of layers and each token $\tau_k \in \mathcal{T}$ is processed by all layers. In contrast, our routing strategy introduces an alternate pathway that allows a subset of tokens to bypass several layers. Specifically, we define a route $\mathbf{r}_{i \rightarrow j}$ (with start layer L_i and end layer L_j) as a bypass of layers L_i, \dots, L_j that is applied to a subset of tokens $\mathcal{T}_r \subset \mathcal{T}$. This results in the routed denoiser

$$D_\theta^{\mathbf{r}_{i \rightarrow j}} = L_{B-1} \circ \dots \circ \begin{cases} \text{id}, & \tau_k \in \mathcal{T}_{\mathbf{r}_{i \rightarrow j}} \\ L_j \circ \dots \circ L_i, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \circ \dots \circ L_0, \quad (4)$$

where $\text{id}(\cdot)$ denotes the identity mapping. The routed tokens $\mathcal{T}_{\mathbf{r}_{i \rightarrow j}}$ are randomly selected for each training sample using a selection rate (see Table 5a). In the special case of $\mathbf{r}_{0 \rightarrow j}$, the routed tokens correspond to the network input.

We integrate routing into the objective Equation (2) as

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{x}_0 \sim p_{\text{data}}} \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{n} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, t^2 \mathbf{I})} \left\| D_\theta^{\mathbf{r}_{i \rightarrow j}}(\mathbf{x}_0 + \mathbf{n}, t) - \mathbf{x}_0 \right\|^2. \quad (5)$$

Unlike masking-based methods—which typically apply a standard diffusion objective to unmasked tokens and a MAE loss to masked tokens to compensate for the irreversible information loss introduced by masking [23]—our approach maintains the simplicity of diffusion models by employing a single reconstruction loss uniformly across all tokens.

Training Efficiency. By skipping the computation of a large number of layers for a substantial fraction of tokens during training, our routing strategy significantly reduces computational cost. Beyond the general linear reduction in computational cost incurred in blocks such as feedforward networks, token routing also enables quadratic gains for self-attention layers. This leads to substantial reductions in computational cost for even small rates of tokens selected for routing. This efficiency gain increases with the route length. Therefore, for maximum computational efficiency, route length should be optimized.

Training Effectiveness. Residual-based architectures, including transformers [22], can interpret outputs from preceding layers [24, 41, 42, 53]. We demonstrate this property in Figure 4, where the cosine similarity between the outputs of all layers in a trained network is shown. This characteristic can be leveraged either to cache layer outputs from previous timesteps for improved inference or to route tokens from one layer to deeper layers, as proposed in TREAD. While diffusion models are typically trained using the same sequence of layers for all samples for each denoising step, TREAD introduces additional variance. Specifically, the second pathway via route $\mathbf{r}_{i \rightarrow j}$ reduces the number of transformations that

Figure 4. **Consecutive layers have highly similar output.** The effects of the routing mechanism are evident in the cosine similarities between layers. For $\mathbf{r}_{3 \rightarrow 8}$, L_2 exhibits high similarity with the routed layers. This is interpreted as an adaptation of L_2 to $\mathbf{r}_{3 \rightarrow 8}$.

are applied to all tokens by the route length. As tokens are randomly selected for routing, the network learns the denoising step with a variable number of layers. This implicitly motivates the network to produce less washed-out features in layer i as they are later being used by layer j directly. Since the network always has access to the standard full pathway (the selection rate for $\mathbf{r}_{i \rightarrow j}$ is less than 1.0), it is beneficial to design the route such that the alternative pathway differs clearly from the standard one as this will increase the above mentioned effect. Good generative performance and low FID (see Figure 6) also correlate strongly with route length. Consequently, longer routes improve both training efficiency and training effectiveness, yielding multiplicative speed-ups (iterations per second \times effectiveness per iteration).

4. Experiment

4.1. Experimental Details

Model Architecture. Our model follows the standard two-stage training process of Latent Diffusion Models (LDM) [54], where an autoencoder is first trained to map between pixel-space and a compressed latent representation. We utilize the pre-trained VAE from Stable Diffusion with a standard downsampling factor of 8. As our method primarily requires token-based processing, we adopt a standard DiT-XL architecture [48] with a patch size of 2 as our main model. Additionally, we demonstrate the generalizability of our approach to other architectures, such as Diffusion-RWKV [14] and Mamba [19]. For ablations we use a DiT-B/2 if not otherwise specified. All modifications are explicitly stated for each experiment. To indicate the application of our method, we append +TREAD to the respective models.

Training Setup. We follow the standard of existing works on diffusion models and train models on ImageNet-256 with a batch size of 256. Furthermore, we follow the standard setting for AdamW from the original DiT [48] with a learning rate of $1e-4$ and no weight decay and the standard β -parameters of 0.9 and 0.999 respectively. We use the standard EMA approach with an update rate of 0.9999. All results are computed using this EMA model. We do not employ any kind of data augmentation. All experiments are conducted on $4 \times 80\text{GB-A100}$ GPUs with a local batch size of 64, resulting in a global batch size of 256, which reflects the standard for ImageNet-256. In addition, we use precomputed latent representations of ImageNet-256, leading to a 32×32 representation. Except for experiments that specifically state otherwise, we apply a selection rate of 50% to our routing mechanism. For Transformer-based structures, we use random selection, while for sequential models like RWKV and Mamba, we find that row selection works better.

Evaluation. Following standard evaluation protocols [48, 72, 75], we primarily evaluate the quality of generated samples using the Fréchet Inception Distance (FID) [25], reporting values on 50,000 samples unless stated otherwise. To ensure fair comparisons with prior works and baselines, we adopt the standard ADM evaluation suite [8]. Additionally, we report the sliced Fréchet Inception Distance (sFID) [9], Inception Score [58], as well as Precision and Recall [57].

4.2. Main Result

Method	Epochs	FID↓	sFID↓	IS↑	Prec.↑	Rec.↑
<i>Unguided</i>						
SD-DiT-XL/2 [76] [†]	480	7.21	5.17	144.68	0.72	0.61
MDT-XL/2 [17] [†]	1300	6.23	5.23	143.02	0.71	0.65
SiT-XL/2 [40]	1400	8.61	6.32	131.65	0.68	0.67
MaskDiT-XL/2 [75] [†]	1600	5.69	10.34	177.99	0.74	0.60
DiT-XL/2 _{+REPA} [72] [†]	170	9.60	-	-	-	-
DiT-XL/2 [48]	1400	9.62	6.85	121.50	0.67	0.67
+TREAD	160	4.96	6.83	192.49	0.79	0.54
+TREAD	680	3.93	7.32	211.35	0.76	0.60
<i>Guided</i>						
SD-DiT-XL/2 [76] [†]	480	3.23	-	-	-	-
MDT-XL/2 [17] [†]	1300	1.79	4.57	283.01	0.81	0.61
MaskDiT-XL/2 [75] [†]	1600	2.28	5.67	276.56	0.80	0.61
SiT-XL/2 [40]	1400	2.06	4.50	270.30	0.82	0.59
DiT-XL/2 [48]	1400	2.27	4.60	278.24	0.83	0.57
+TREAD(F)	220	2.76	4.61	252.78	0.83	0.57
+TREAD(F)	740	2.09	4.46	269.07	0.81	0.62
+TREAD(F)[‡]	740	1.69	4.73	292.66	0.81	0.63

([†]) alters the architecture or uses additional parameters. ([‡]) uses interval guidance [33].

Table 1. **Performance comparison on ImageNet-256.** Applying TREAD to the standard DiT results in *faster convergence* while being *substantially cheaper* to train. TREAD outperforms various baselines including those with additional parameters and architectural changes. Selected samples from DiT-XL/2_{+TREAD} (F) can be found in Figure 2.

General Comparison. We conduct a comprehensive evaluation against state-of-the-art approaches that focus on enhancing *training effectiveness*, such as MDT [17] and SD-DiT [76], as well as methods that prioritize *efficiency* by accelerating iterative training, such as MaskDiT [75]. Our results show that TREAD outperforms the standard DiT [48] in both aspects, achieving faster convergence while maintaining high efficiency and also outperforms state-of-the-art baselines in their respective domain. We refer readers to Figure 1 for a visual representation of our model’s superior performance. Specifically, w.g.t. *training effectiveness*, our approach significantly outperforms both MDT and SD-DiT while we achieve higher *training efficiency* through a increased iteration rate (3.03it/s), thus reducing computational costs compared to MaskDiT (2.98it/s), the baseline DiT (1.86it/s), and MDT (1.02it/s) under identical conditions. Our efficiency is also shown in Table 1, where TREAD

Figure 5. **TREAD shows good performance at low compute cost.** We demonstrate a strictly better performance-cost trade-off than all other presented methods, including DiT+REPA [72]. For methods with (*), we assume an identical iteration speed to the DiT. This is advantageous for our competitors as those utilize additional parameters or entire pre-trained vision encoders to aid their diffusion model, effectively decreasing their iteration speed.

demonstrates accelerated convergence and superior performance. In the unguided setting, our approach not only accelerates training but also improves performance while reducing computational costs (see Figure 5). In the guided setting, we first train the model with TREAD and then fine-tune it without routing to improve its response to classifier-free guidance (CFG). This follows the well-documented phenomenon that restricting information during training can degrade performance under CFG [75, 76]. While our method outperforms prior work and the standard DiT without fine-tuning in the guided setting (see Appendix Figure S9), we still observe an improved CFG response after a subsequent fine-tuning stage without routing. To this end, we adopt the fine-tuning strategy from Zheng et al. [75], using a batch size of 1,024 and a reduced learning rate for 75K iterations.

Comparison with Base Architectures. We demonstrate the effectiveness of our approach in improving efficiency and performance while showcasing its adaptability to diverse architectures. To illustrate this, we use RWKV [49], which shares many aspects of SSMs and employs a RNN-like structure, which makes it fundamentally different from the transformer-based DiT. As shown in Table 2, our method consistently outperforms the baseline models across both architectures. Notably, the performance gains are also pronounced in larger models, indicating the scalability of our approach and its suitability for larger architectures. We also expand TREAD beyond EDM [32] to flowmatching [1, 37, 40] and find that our method transfers well to other frameworks. All models, except those denoted as "SiT" in Table 2 and Table 5b are trained using EDM to remain comparable to our baselines and competitors. We also extend our experiments beyond ImageNet-256 to ImageNet-512 to investigate the impact of larger token counts (see Table 4).

Model	#Param	Iter.	Batchsize	FID↓
DiT-S/2 [48]	33M	400K	256	68.40
+ TREAD	33M	400K	256	47.04 _{+21.36}
SiT-S/2 [39]	33M	400K	256	57.60
+ TREAD	33M	400K	256	38.08 _{+19.52}
DiT-B/2 [48]	130M	400K	256	43.47
+ TREAD	130M	400K	256	21.34 _{+22.13}
SiT-B/2 [39]	130M	400K	256	33.00
+ TREAD	130M	400K	256	15.98 _{+16.02}
DiT-L/2 [48]	458M	400K	256	23.33
+ TREAD	458M	400K	256	9.10 _{+14.23}
SiT-L/2 [39]	458M	400K	256	18.80
+ TREAD	458M	400K	256	5.91 _{+12.89}
DiT-XL/2 [48]	675M	400K	256	19.47
+ TREAD	675M	400K	256	7.38 _{+12.09}
SiT-XL/2 [39]	675M	400K	256	17.20
+ TREAD	675M	400K	256	4.89 _{+12.31}
RWKV [14]	210M	400K	256	59.84
+ TREAD	210M	400K	256	53.79 _{+6.05}
Mamba [15]	111M	400K	256	69.39
+ TREAD	111M	400K	256	61.17 _{+8.22}

Table 2. **Performance increase across all model configurations** trained up to 400K iterations on ImageNet-256 (batch size 256).

Compounding Gains with Representation Distillation.

As TREAD does not modify the base architecture and, unlike masking-based methods, does not incur information loss, it is naturally orthogonal to other changes in diffusion training and can thus be combined with them. We evaluate this by combining TREAD with REPA [72], a state-of-the-art method that incorporates representation distillation from a pretrained vision backbone [46] as a secondary objective to improve diffusion models. As shown in Table 3, the combination of both methods results in better generation performance (as indicated by a lower FID) than each achieves individually. The reduced costs and improved effectiveness through TREAD enable compounding gains when combined with other diffusion training methods.

Model	Iter.	FID ↓
DiT-B/2		43.47
+ REPA		34.63
+ TREAD	400K	21.34
+ TREAD + REPA		20.06 _{+1.28}
<i>Further Training + Unguided</i>		
+ REPA		28.86
+ TREAD	800K	15.87
+ TREAD + REPA		13.76 _{+2.37}
<i>Further Training + Guided</i>		
+ REPA		9.04
+ TREAD	800K	6.39
+ TREAD + REPA		5.62 _{+0.77}

Table 3. **Combining the TREAD training strategy with REPA** to demonstrate that our method’s modular design enables combination with orthogonal approaches to further improve performance.

Figure 6. **Early training loss strongly correlates with FID improvements.** Our analysis indicates that route length shows a strong correlation with both the FID and early training loss. Consequently, the observed correlation between training loss and FID can be attributed to route length acting as a hidden variable.

Scaling to Larger Resolutions and Text-to-Image. We also investigate the scalability and general applicability of TREAD by validating it in higher-resolution and more general settings. Specifically, we evaluate on ImageNet-512 and T2I MS-COCO (2014) [36]. We train DiT-B/2 models with and without TREAD for 400K iterations each using a batchsize of 256 and evaluate using FID@10k for both. We find that our method leads to substantial gains in generative performance, reducing FID by more than a third (as indicated in Table 4), while also leading to substantially faster training due to a significant increase in iteration speed.

4.3. Ablation Study

We conduct multiple ablation studies to examine the effect that each component has on the performance of TREAD. All experiments are conducted using a DiT-B/2 model and evaluated using 50,000 samples if not otherwise specified.

Route Location. In Figure 8, we present results from a set of DiT-B/2 models trained with different routes $\mathbf{r}_{i \rightarrow j}$. We conduct two ablations: first, by fixing $i = 0$ and varying the end layer j , and second, by fixing $j = 8$ and varying the starting layer i . From these experiments, we observe two distinct modes: one where routing improves performance

Model	#Param	Iter.	Batchsize	FID@10K ↓
<i>ImageNet-512</i>				
DiT	130M	400K	256	62.88
+ TREAD	130M	400K	256	40.91 _{+21.97}
<i>MS-COCO</i>				
DiT	130M	400K	256	35.68
+ TREAD	130M	400K	256	20.55 _{+15.13}

Table 4. **Application of TREAD to high-resolution class conditional generation and text-to-image generation.** We demonstrate TREAD’s effectiveness is transferable to other generative diffusion tasks like high-resolution ImageNet-512 and T2I MS-COCO. For both experiments we use a DiT-B/2 and DiT-B/2+TREAD.

Figure 7. **Routes should start early and end in time.** This results in longer routes and allows the model to spend reasonable remaining capacity to reintegrate the routed tokens. This is clearly demonstrated as later start indices (i) and earlier ending indices (j) correlate with worse generative performance (measured with FID).

and one where it does not. Since these modes are clearly separable, we can derive principles for route placement to enhance training effectiveness. Specifically, we find that **i)** longer routes generally lead to better performance, **ii)** starting layers up to $i = 2$ improve results, and **iii)** ending layers up to $j = 8$ are beneficial. Additionally, the configuration $\mathbf{r}_{i=0, j=10}$ demonstrates that choosing an excessively late end location j can be detrimental to performance, as the network requires sufficient capacity to integrate routed tokens into the overall information flow. Whenever routing does not lead to lower FID, we can attribute the observed effect to violating at least one of these principles. In the case of TREAD, we can optimize both training effectiveness and training efficiency simultaneously. According to our route placement guidelines, training effectiveness can be increased with longer routes. At the same time, longer routes accelerate training speed by increasing the number of layers processing fewer tokens compared to DiT [48]. In Figure 6, we present our findings from this analysis. Our results indicate that route length is strongly correlated with both FID and training loss, even at early stages. Consequently, early training loss also exhibits a strong correlation with FID. Additionally to the usual diffusion loss we see an offset caused by the route that indicates its impact on the model. Furthermore, we provide a custom baseline in Table 5b where we compare TREAD against token-level dropout in each layer to underline the importance of route configuration. We also demonstrate the importance of the start layer i and end layer j in Figure 7, where we show the generative performance for models with the respective route placement settings. Notably, there is a trend for both where the best results were achieved using $i = 2$ and $j = 8$, with deviations following a clear downwards direction in terms of FID (except for $j = 10$).

Selection Rate. In this experiment, we ablate the impact of the selection ratio on performance, as shown in Table 5a, where the selection ratio is defined in the range $\in [0, 1]$. We specifically exclude 1.0 as it would entirely skip layers of the network, leaving substantial parts untrained. We ablate in increments of 0.25. We observe a significant performance

Figure 8. **Longer routes lead to better performance.** We evaluate DiT-B/2 models trained for 400K iterations using FID@5K. The results show that FID improves as the route length increases. The lowest FID values are associated with longer routes, early start layers, and relatively late end layers. However, we find that there exists a breakpoint when end layers are chosen too late, as the network requires enough capacity to incorporate routed tokens.

improvement when using a random selection rate of 0.25 (FID = 26.50) and 0.5 (FID = 21.34), both outperforming the vanilla DiT-B/2 (FID = 43.47) while also reducing computational cost per iteration. Interestingly, the medium selection rate of 0.5 achieves a lower FID than 0.25. However, a higher selection rate of 0.75 (FID = 49.29) leads to degraded performance, performing worse than the vanilla model. This aligns with our explanation in Section 3, as the selection rate affects the influence of the alternative token pathway during training. In addition, a high selection rate causes fewer tokens to be processed in each layer affected by the route, leading to better training efficiency.

Selection Rate	FID ↓	Model	FID ↓
0 (DiT-B/2)	43.47	SiT-B/2 [39]	33.00
0.25	26.50 ∇ 16.97	TLDrop	32.00
0.50	21.34 ∇ 22.13	TLDropR	24.28
0.75	49.29 \blacktriangle 5.82	+TREAD (absolute)	15.98

(a) Selection Rate Ablation .

(b) Token-level dropout vs. TREAD.

Table 5. **Ablation and Baseline Comparison.** (a) shows the effect of selection rate on FID on DiT-B/2+TREAD. (b) compares token-level dropout over all layers (TLDrop), over layers 2 → 8 (TLDropR) and our long-route TREAD. In all cases, the dropout resembles a route of length 1.

Model	FID ↓
DiT-XL/2	
+TREAD (relative)	18.81
+TREAD (absolute)	7.38

Table 6. **Location choice transfers from DiT-B/2 to large models like DiT-XL/2.** We extend our insights from Figure 8 to larger models by using relative settings ($i = \frac{1}{6}, j = \frac{2}{3}$) and absolute settings ($i = 2, j = B - 4$) based on the optimal configuration of DiT-B/2. We find the absolute setting to achieve the best performance.

Extrapolating Route Location to Large Models. For the B/2 model, we find the optimal route to be $r_{i=2 \rightarrow j=8}$ as shown in Figure 8. To extend these findings to larger models with additional layers, two strategies are considered: *Relative Extrapolation*: In this approach, the indices are scaled proportionally to the total number of layers, resulting in $i = \frac{2}{12} = \frac{1}{6}$ and $j = \frac{8}{12} = \frac{2}{3}$. *Absolute Configuration*: Here, the starting index is fixed at $i = 2$ and the ending index is chosen as $j = B - 4$, where B represents the total number of layers. These approaches aim to determine whether the optimal routing configuration identified in the B/2 model can be effectively generalized to larger models. As shown in Table 6, the DiT-XL/2+TREAD model trained using the absolute extrapolation approach achieves superior performance. This substantial performance gap suggests that the optimal route location scales in an absolute, or near-absolute, manner with larger model sizes.

5. Conclusion

Training diffusion models remains computationally expensive, even as recent methods leverage accelerated inference, fine-tuning, and personalization. We propose TREAD, a diffusion training strategy that integrates into token-based sequential models without architectural modifications. By routing tokens from early to later layers, TREAD improves generation quality while reducing computational cost at the same time. This leads to a total speed-up to standard training of $37\times$. We systematically explore its design space, derive empirically validated guidelines, and demonstrate that it accelerates convergence on class-conditional ImageNet-256 by an order of magnitude compared to standard training. Our extensive experiments show that TREAD can be applied to current state-of-the-art methods, like representation distillation, to further improve training effectiveness, enabling future work in this field for a greater number of researchers.

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